

ROLE OF SOCIETY IN CONSERVATION OF NATURAL RESOURCES

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INTRODUCTION

Anything in the environment which can be used is called a 'natural resource'. Protecting the environment from destruction is called conservation of environment.

Some of our important natural resources are forest, wildlife, water, coal & petroleum.

The resources of the earth are limited because of the rapid increase in population. The demand for resources is increasing day by day. The proper management can ensure that the natural resources are used judiciously so that they fulfill the needs of present generation and also last for the generations to come.

Water is the basic necessity for all forms of life, human beings other animals as well as plants. The various sources of water are: Rain, Rivers, Lakes, Ponds, Wells, Oceans and Glaciers. Rain is a very important source of water. Rains in India are largely due to monsoon which, lasts for a few months. High yielding Varieties of crops require more water for irrigation. The changing life style of people is consuming more water so we are not able to fulfill the demand of water for all people. Rivers are another important source of water. The management of river water is done by constructing dams on rivers. Dams are useful for the society because of irrigation, water supply in towns and cities, generating electricity.

The public opposition on the construction of large dams on rivers is mainly due to some problems. Due to construction of dams a large number of human settlements are submerged in the water of large reservoir formed by the dam and many people are rendered homeless. It also contributes to deforestation and loss of biodiversity.

The water of most of rivers is highly polluted. The pollution of river water is caused by the dumping of untreated sewage and industrial water into it.

Wells and tube wells are other sources of water. This water is used for the irrigation of crops and for drinking purpose.

Rain water harvesting is necessary for saving water. The people in rural India have used a large number of water collecting methods to capture as much rainwater as possible which had fallen on their land. Some of the methods used for this were: Digging of small pits and lakes, Building of small earthen dams, construction of long wall of earth to trap water, construction of sand and limestone reservoirs and setting up of roof top water collecting units. All these methods of collecting and saving rain water have recharged the depleting ground water levels.

- The advantage of rain water harvesting is that it increases the availability of ground water and helps in overcoming water shortage.
- Role of society is very important in uplifting natural environment.
- Rivers, lakes and other water sources should not be polluted.
- Used water can be treated in the water treatment plants & used again

- Eco-friendly materials should be used to minimize pollution & encourage natural environment.
- The excessive and indiscriminate use of various types of natural resources is spoiling our healthy environment day by day. We can save our environment by practicing three R's: Reduce, Recycle and reuse.
- In cities greenery should be encouraged.
- Use of fossil fuels like coal & petroleum should be minimized and natural gas, CNC should be encouraged.

REFERENCES

1. धनंजय वर्मा : पर्यावरण चेतना : म.प्र. हिन्दी ग्रंथ अकादमी /
- 2- Lakhmir singh and Manjit kaur: *Biology S Chand & company pvt. Ltd. N. Delhi.*
3. सक्सेना एस. एम. एवं सीमा मोहन : पर्यावरण अध्ययन 2013, कैलाश पुस्तक सदन भोपाल /
4. शुक्ला त्रिभुवन नाथ : पर्यावरण अध्ययन, म.प्र. हिन्दी ग्रंथ अकादमी भोपाल /
- 5- Surana Narendramal: *Enrивonmental studies, S B P D pub. House Agra.*